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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT: A WAY TO GROW AND GET HELP”

The Master of Arts in Education course in Educational Management broadens our understanding of how school organization, supervision, and administration work while also preparing us for leadership roles by teaching us efficient school management techniques. This class teaches us how to work with others, do our jobs well, and act appropriately.

This class has changed how I think about school leadership roles. To me, administration was just paperwork, planning, and keeping an eye on other people. But I learned that it's more than just running things. It stresses creating an environment where students can thrive, building trust, and giving teachers more power. I now understand how hiring, planning, and evaluating a school's staff can affect how well it does as a whole.

It was a hard journey. I was a teacher, Katherine Jane's husband, and the father of our son Carl Ezrael. I had a lot on my plate while I worked toward a higher degree. There were times when schoolwork and family duties were both going on at the same time. I was able to get through the problems by planning my work, thinking ahead about what I would do next, and getting better at acting quickly. My family also gave me strength when things got tough.

The most important thing I learned in this class is that good leadership is based on self-governance and personal growth. "He who goes about to reform the world must begin with himself," said Saint Ignatius of Loyola. I like this idea because I believe that true leadership begins with the person. Being honest, helpful, and good at everything you do shows it.

This experience will help me a lot in the future as a teacher and leader. I now see myself as a teacher who can help make the classroom a moral and useful place to learn, guide my peers, and make a difference. With God's help and the support of my family and friends, I know that what I've learned in Educational Management will be the foundation of my career as a leader and teacher for the rest of my life.

